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**MUTUAL MEANING OF SIMILAR WORDS USED IN A WORK OF
ART (BASED ON THE WORKS OF OTKIR HASHIMOV)**

Abdullayeva Ozoda

named after Sharof Rashidov Student of Samarkand State University

Telefon: +998935038650

abdullayevaozoda787@gmail.com

Abstract: This article talks about the mutual synonymy of imitative words used in artistic works and their importance as one of the methodological tools in ensuring the expressiveness, expressiveness, and artistic value of the work.

Key words: Imitative words, synonymy, nuances of meaning, speech situation, neutral meaning, emotional-expressiveness.

A language often uses a number of imitative words to express the sound of something or the image of an action. This is the phenomenon of synonymy (4,44), which ensures that imitative words are an important methodological tool in the artistic text. In stylistics, semantics has a great position and importance.

The lexical-semantic diversity of the language of the work of art, the application of a certain norm in the language of the author and characters is related to the individual style of the writer. When using linguistic units, the writer tries to use words and phrases that clearly express the character, behavior and state of the person he is describing, and clearly embody in the eyes of the reader. The use of language units in the artistic work that match the spirit of the text ensures that the language of the work is attractive and impressive. At the same time, this phenomenon is often referred to in fiction in order to avoid repetition. The phenomenon of synonymy has developed widely in the system of imitative words. In the works of the people's writer of Uzbekistan O'tkir Hashimov, there is a lot of reference to imitative words in the process of describing people's speech, their mood, mental state and appearance, as well as their various relationships with the objective existence that surrounds a person. In his works, Adib skillfully used several imitative words to express a certain situation, which made the work of art more educated and popular.

For example, in the literary works, several synonymous imitation words are used to express a single state of laughter: hih-hi-ho, hi-hi-hi, voh-ho-ho, kah-kah, ha-ha-ha, squealing, hoo-hoo-lab, humming, hex-hex-hex, hex like. - Hee-hee-hee! - Shaidul the

cashier straightened up and laughed. - Ha-ha-ha! The money I gave! (I.274). Nargis Khan burst out laughing (I. 271). The "Fairy" stared for a minute or two with his eyelashes still fluttering, then threw himself on the back of the chair and started laughing (I.232). After that, Ana suddenly threw herself back, fell on Shodivoy's bed and began to behave abnormally. When I looked closer, he was laughing. "Hih-hi-ho!", "Hi-hi-hi!", "Woh-ho-ho!" (I.208). - Don't bother! - Aunt Parcha looked over her shoulder at the women standing behind her and laughed heartily. - I'll fix everything myself! (II. 113). As soon as Panshakha sank into my stomach, I was tickled and laughed hysterically (I.157). The commissioner laughed. His laugh is strange. He says "hex-hex-hex" as if he were talking about a person (III. 9). - Heh! - The commissar laughed sarcastically. - it's all the same! (III.127).

In all the examples, imitation words are used to describe the state of laughter. But the phenomena represented by these imitation words cannot be considered as completely the same. Although several synonymous words serve to indicate the same phenomenon, the meaning of each synonymous word differs from the other with its certain subtleties of meaning. That is, the sound of laughing and laughing cannot be interpreted as the same.

To represent the sound of a step: Imitations such as kars-kurs, ship-ship, gurs-gurs, tars-turs, slap-shap, slap-shup, tap-tap were used. The blessed heels of your bride are clattering in the silent hall (I, 251). At that moment, footsteps were heard in the back (I, 199). Step by step steps began to go around the grave (I, 159). When I look like this while standing on all fours, our teacher's sister is running in the dark corridor. His heels are "twirling" and "twirling" (I, 133). His slippers clattered on the porch, and the door of the other room was heard opening (I, 47). I found out that my father went to the yard. He hurriedly went to the door and returned immediately (II, 54). Who is your brother walking ahead on the dirt street, tapping his feet (II, 84). To explain the sound of coughing: like, khuk-khuv: Is it possible to cough at the same time when pressing the palatal? ...-Oh, oh, oh! I choked. (I. 215). That night, on the side of the children's bed, there was a coughing fit. (III. 17).

To express the state of crying: yum-yum, ukrab, chuvvos, duv-duv, like: That night, Naziri had a dream... Although he didn't speak, he was crying all the time (III, 145). The commissar burst into tears (III, 142). Everyone was shocked. Dad pressed

my head to his chest and cried (II, 43). He crawled on his knees and begged with tears streaming down his eyes (III, 120).

To express the speech sounds of people: Gala-guvur, kugur-кугур, кии-чув, гувур-гувур, шувур, gangur-gungur, visir-visir, ghovur- murmur, murmur, murmur, whisper, murmur like illab: At the same time a commotion broke out in the classroom (I.173). - Let's go! - Grandmother Rais shouted in such a way that the people who were constantly shouting became silent like sparrows hearing the sound of gunshots. (I. 205). Calves are bleating somewhere, and the squeals of school children can be heard from the other side (I.13). The surroundings are filled with the noise of revelers and the noise of trams and trolleybuses (I.20). Today the restaurant was sparsely populated, but the hall was full of noise as usual (I.107). When I go out to the porch and take off my boots, there is a lot of chatter inside (I. 246). - Wow, my teacher! - Jerkib said, his voice booming in the microphone. -Sit quietly, okay? (I.269). Their wedding will be strange. A day before, it was noisy under the roof at night. Shuvir-shusur... (III. 41). While he was digging potatoes, he heard a German whisper about ten paces away (III. 59). One day, he read the notebook, which was stained with tears, to a close friend. The two of them enter a room and whisper to each other... (III. 67). The boy followed the dog, muttering in his own language while still crying (III. 106). Let him pretend that he is a suspect who defended the "enemy of the people"! (III. 129). The children's tongues came out one by one, they went on the road (III. 139). On the other hand, the Second One tied a string to the sensitive area of the First One. Let it be your first time! He pulls the second thread. (III. 176). A man of color. They talked in whispers (II. 51). My mother mumbled everything and went back to the yard (II, 123). "Geographical atlas, brother Tursunboy," I mumbled. - Atlas of history. To the exam. (I. 166). Domullo! A voice rang out saying, "What a fool!" - What are you doing torturing the children? Hurry up. The cloth is falling (I.173).

It can be seen from the given examples that the semantic relations expressed by the imitative words used in these cases are not the same. Depending on the speech situation, some of them have a neutral meaning, while some of them serve to express strong emotional-expressive (emotional-affective) coloring: 1. Calves are bleating somewhere, and the squealing sounds of school children are heard from the other side (I. 13). 2. - Oh, my teacher! - Jerkib said, his voice booming in the microphone. -Sit quietly, okay? (I.269). Although the above sentences use imitative words related to the

speech situation of people, the imitative word "kii-chuv" in the first sentence expresses a stylistically neutral meaning, while the word "visir-visir" in the second sentence zi has negative coloring.

Thus, our beloved writer O'tkir Hashimov referred to synonymous imitative words in his works and used them appropriately as one of the important methodological tools to ensure the impact, expressiveness, and artistry of the thought, and to increase the value of the work.

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